

EXAMINING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF YOUTUBE ADVERTISEMENTS OF FOOD PANDA AND GRAB ON CONSUMER PURCHASING INTENTIONS

Shaira Marie A. Eligino, Jay-vee B. Aruelo, Alyssa Marie D. Damayo,
Sharon Mae D. Delfin, Ma. Annie Moriel D. Engbino, Princess Mae Jovelo,
Bryan R. Obedice

*College of Business and Accountancy
Our Lady of Fatima University
Valenzuela City, Philippines*

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ABSTRACT

In the digital era, the battle for consumer attention has shifted to a new frontier: YouTube. Brands wielding captivating videos now strive to influence our purchasing decisions through carefully crafted advertisements. This study dives into the murky waters of online video marketing, examining the effectiveness of YouTube advertisements on consumer purchasing intentions. This topic piqued the researchers' interest which led to examining the effectiveness of YouTube advertisements by two prominent food delivery applications, namely, Food Panda and Grab, on consumer purchasing intentions of the respondents within Metro Manila who have watched their advertisements for the last two weeks using the four variables namely: Content and Quality, External Factors, Influence Level, and Frequency of Viewings. The surveys were distributed through Google forms and the results were analyzed based on the collected data. The findings found that YouTube advertisements had an impact on the purchasing decisions of respondents and the variables that were utilized in the research were significant contributors to this influence. Additionally, the highest key contributor is the Frequency of Viewings from Grab YouTube Advertisement which has a Pearson correlation of 0.887. The results of this study can provide valuable insights for marketers, advertisers, and decision-makers within these companies.

Keywords: *YouTube, Advertisement, Purchasing decision, Food Panda, Grab, Consumer, Brand, Effectiveness, Application, Influence*

INTRODUCTION

In the ever-evolving landscape of digital marketing, the influence of online platforms on consumer behavior has become increasingly significant. This study delves into the effectiveness of YouTube advertisements, specifically those of two prominent food delivery services—Food Panda and Grab. The focus is on understanding how these advertisements impact consumer purchasing intentions. As consumers continue to turn to online platforms for information and decision-making, dissecting the strategies employed by leading brands in this space provides valuable insights into the dynamics of digital advertising and its implications on consumer choices. This research aims to shed light on the nuanced effectiveness of YouTube advertisements in the highly competitive realm of food delivery services.

Examining the effectiveness of Foodpanda and Grab YouTube advertisements in influencing consumer purchasing intentions is crucial for several reasons. Firstly, YouTube has become a dominant platform for consuming online video content according to Suciu (2021), reaching a vast and diverse audience. Understanding how these food delivery giants utilize YouTube advertising to capture consumer attention and drive purchasing decisions is essential in the competitive food delivery landscape. Secondly, according to Soti (2022), analyzing the effectiveness of these advertisements provides valuable insights into consumer behavior and preferences. By understanding how consumers respond to different advertising strategies, Foodpanda and Grab can optimize their campaigns to better resonate with their target audience. Furthermore, examining the effectiveness of YouTube advertising can inform broader marketing strategies for both Foodpanda and Grab. Understanding the strengths and weaknesses of their current advertising approach allows them to make informed decisions about resource allocation and campaign development (FrogDog Magazine, 2021). This can lead to more effective and efficient use of marketing resources, maximizing their return on investment (Sathupati, 2023).

This study assessed the impact of Foodpanda and Grab YouTube advertisements on consumer purchasing intentions, employing a multifaceted approach. By analyzing the content and strategies of each company's YouTube ads, the research scrutinized visual elements, messaging, and storytelling techniques to gauge their efficacy in capturing consumer attention and conveying brand messages. Surveys, focus groups, and interviews explored consumer perceptions and responses to these advertisements, shedding light on engagement levels and the likelihood of choosing Foodpanda or Grab based on the ads. The study also identified key factors contributing to the effectiveness of each company's YouTube advertisements, considering elements like brand perception, emotional appeal, and the effectiveness of calls to action. Ultimately, the findings informed recommendations for both Foodpanda and Grab, offering insights on how to

optimize their YouTube advertising strategies, enhance consumer engagement, and drive purchasing decisions.

This study holds significant importance as it aims to thoroughly investigate the impact of YouTube advertisements by two major players in the food delivery industry, namely Food Panda and Grab, on consumer purchasing intentions. In the contemporary landscape, where digital advertising is pervasive, understanding the effectiveness of these platforms is crucial for businesses (Gomez, 2023), striving to capture consumer attention and drive actual purchase decisions. The findings of this research can provide valuable insights for marketers, advertisers, and decision-makers within these companies. Understanding which elements, such as visual content, messaging, and storytelling strategies, contribute most significantly to influencing consumer behavior can inform the optimization of future advertising campaigns. Moreover, delving into consumer perceptions and responses offers a nuanced understanding of the effectiveness of these advertisements beyond mere viewership numbers. By enhancing consumer engagement and driving purchasing decisions, the study contributes not only to the academic understanding of advertising effectiveness but also offers practical implications for businesses seeking to navigate the ever-evolving digital landscape.

Literature Review

A study conducted by Firat (2019), demonstrates that one of the best advertising tools to attract consumers was advertisements and one of the greatest platforms to attract consumers was YouTube. The variable that can be led on the advertisement ineffectively is irritability where customers find the advertisements boring and interrupting what they were doing in YouTube. In addition to this, there are variables that advertisement is effective to a customer where the advertisement in YouTube helps customers find their need and wants by providing accurate information about the business, products, services, or brand. The findings indicated that the purchasing intention of customers where the content in YouTube is perceived credibility, usefulness and provides facts and information about the products that are promoted on their channel and it positively affect the purchasing intention of the customers.

It appears to be set against the backdrop of YouTube's immense popularity and the potential it offers as an advertising platform, particularly when targeting younger audiences. It addresses a significant gap in the existing literature by exploring the impact of YouTube advertising on advertisement value and purchase intention. A well-designed study with a rigorous methodology and clear findings can provide valuable insights to marketers and advertisers, helping them make more informed decisions about their digital advertising strategies. Results demonstrate that it likely delves into the effectiveness of YouTube advertising in influencing customers' intentions to make purchases. (Ashraf et al., 2021).

In a study conducted among the consumers in Chennai, Dr. Zarina et al., (2021) unearthed pivotal insights regarding the effects of YouTube advertisements on buying behavior. Their research demonstrated that while aspects like product introduction,

attractiveness, entertainment, and detailed information bolstered motivation and influenced purchasing positively, the feature of unskippable advertisements negatively impacted brand recognition, indirectly affecting motivation and overall buying behavior. Essentially, over 30% of the participants paid attention to YouTube advertisements, underlining the platform's efficacy in advertising. However, unskippable advertisements stood out as a deterrent, suggesting advertisers should be wary of such inclusions. The study's results stress the importance of how YouTube advertisements are presented and their substantial role in influencing buying decisions, emphasizing the need for brands to strategize carefully to optimize consumer engagement and drive positive buying behaviors.

YouTube's role as a prominent advertising platform was examined in a study led by Sebastian et al., (2021) to understand viewers' perceptions of advertisements and their influence on purchase intent among Indian netizens. Their qualitative research, involving 50 participants who frequently engage with YouTube, unveiled four principal themes: the relevance of advertisements, disinterest, subjective distress, and the balance between information and entertainment. Findings indicate that viewers experience subjective distress from recurrent, misplaced, and overly long advertisements. Conversely, advertisements that introduce products innovatively or showcase distinctive creativity enhance the viewing experience, often encouraging repeat views and potentially influencing purchasing decisions. The rise of YouTube premium, especially among India's middle class, adds another layer to the advertising dynamic, suggesting future research could probe deeper into socio-economic influences on ad perceptions.

The effectiveness of YouTube advertising on young customers' purchasing decisions was the central theme of a study conducted by Aziza and Astuti (2019). Through an in-depth exploration, they identified that advertisements which were deemed entertaining significantly boosted the perceived value of YouTube advertising. Interestingly, while these factors proved influential, the anticipated roles of customization and irritation didn't show any significant effect on the advertising value. A crucial finding was that the overall value of YouTube advertising had a notable positive impact on customers' intent to purchase. Moreover, the presence of brand awareness was found to partially mediate this relationship. Given these insights, companies aiming to leverage YouTube for advertising should prioritize content that is engaging.

Chotigo and Kadono's (2021) study focuses on understanding the factors propelling Thai consumers to adopt food delivery apps, with a specific emphasis on contrasting behaviors before and during the COVID-19 pandemic. Using the modified Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology 2 (UTAUT2) model, the research evaluated factors such as trust, convenience, app quality, and overall user satisfaction. Data collected from two distinct samples revealed that customer satisfaction was primarily driven by factors like social influence, trust, convenience, and the app's quality, regardless of the pandemic's presence. Intriguingly, while price was a significant determinant of satisfaction prior to the pandemic, it lost its importance during the pandemic. Simultaneously, habitual use had a positive effect on satisfaction pre-pandemic, but during the pandemic, it showed a negative correlation. Consistently, in both scenarios,

satisfied users were more inclined to continue using the app. These insights underscore the critical role of user experience and satisfaction in the adoption and consistent use of food delivery apps, especially in dynamic situations like the ongoing pandemic.

The intricate relationship between online food delivery applications (OFD) quality attributes and the emotions they induce in users plays a significant role in determining their continued usage intentions. In a study conducted by Handayani, Azzizah, and Annisa (2022), it was uncovered that the app's convenience is directly tied to users experiencing feelings of pleasure, excitement, and dominance. Conversely, while the app's price information affected users' feelings of control, it didn't elicit emotions of pleasure or excitement. Notably, the trustworthiness of an OFD had no considerable impact on any of the studied emotions. Ultimately, users' intentions to continuously engage with an OFD were influenced by their feelings of happiness, arousal, and control during its use.

The goal of Yao's (2023) study was to assess how consumers seek information of the two attributes to be able to judge the various features of a product. As a result of the study, it has been found that, due to the quicker learning speed, consumers are always best placed to seek out an attribute they have greater uncertainty about. Only when consumers have a strong confidence in one or the other of those attributes, and are able to search for either attribute independently, will they be likely to seek an even more uncertain attribute. Then they demonstrate how firms are influencing consumer search behavior, and making them more profitable by means of informational advertising.

In a study conducted by Ahmad and Lasi (2020), the effects of social network formation, viral marketing has emerged as a new, widespread method of consumption for residents of Subang Jaya. Malaysia is one of the nations and territories where Foodpanda, a German mobile food delivery service with its headquarters in Berlin, is active. The five variables are as follows: i) perceived informativeness, ii) perceived amusement, perceived annoyance, and perceived source credibility and v) the impression of incentives. They have substantial impacts of viral marketing on customer attitudes in Subang Jaya, in the city of Malaysia.

A recent study by Irshad et al., (2022) concluded that FoodPanda, a well-known food delivery service, has successfully resonated with customers through its strategic use of social media channels for promotional and advertising objectives, leading to higher levels of satisfaction among its user base. This highlights the growing significance of social media engagement and digital marketing in the context of the food delivery industry, since they have the potential to significantly improve consumer satisfaction and increase brand loyalty. These findings acknowledge the goal of this study to identify the impact of using social media and the importance of building a customer relationship, as well as creating brand image.

A study delved into understanding the credibility of Consumer-Generated advertisements (CGAs) on YouTube and their sway on Filipino consumers. Through a virtual focus group discussion encompassing fifteen diverse Filipino participants, it

emerged that product review videos wield a potent influence on viewers' purchasing behaviors. Most viewers employ these reviews as evaluative tools before committing to a product purchase. A significant revelation was the participants' discerning nature; while YouTube is a vast reservoir of information, not all of it was deemed credible. Authenticity, neutrality, comprehensive pros and cons analysis, and tangible proof of product use were essential for a review's credibility. Furthermore, a video's value was tied to metrics like views, likes, and subscriber count, and the communicator's proficiency in presenting. In essence, honest, well-researched, and unbiased content held the power to mold buying intentions (Dacudao et al., 2022).

The research by Arellano et al., (2022) investigated the profound influence of social media marketing on the purchasing behaviors of Filipinos. Leveraging a qualitative approach, the study elucidated how various demographics—students, employees, and parents—respond differently to social media-driven advertisements. Notably, students, engrossed by their digital environments, often exhibited impulsive buying tendencies, influenced by advertisements presented to them. In contrast, employed individuals displayed a more practical stance, their purchasing decisions anchored to their budgetary confines, stemming from their monetary responsibilities. In sum, while individual preferences played a role in buying behaviors, the study underscored the escalating dependency on social media in influencing these decisions.

According to Cabuslay (2021), it is not surprising that brands have shown a growing interest in creating content that can keep viewers engaged during periods of lockdown when people spend more time on their devices. Episodic content has become a popular strategy for engaging and retaining audiences. This approach is often used in various forms of online content, such as web series, vlogs, and serialized storytelling on platforms like YouTube or social media. The idea is to keep the audience coming back for more by creating a sense of anticipation and curiosity with each new installment or video snippet. This can be an effective way to engage and retain viewers in today's digital media landscape.

The study by Damle and Nandi (2020) shows that it is through the measurement of consumer attitudes to digital advertising that the primary aim of this research is to establish factors contributing to consumers' purchasing decisions. The importance of internet media for the efficiency of digital advertising and consumer approach is also justified. The result of the calculations carried out in relation to the conducted research is that the effectiveness of online media platforms is substantially influenced by them.

Furthermore, Dalangin et al., (2021) study explored the role of social media influencers in shaping consumers' purchase intentions in the Philippines. The findings highlighted that an influencer's perceived honesty and trustworthiness significantly influence consumers' buying behaviors and intentions. Additionally, the study underscored the importance of an influencer's attractiveness and genuine relationship with the product they are promoting. A positive correlation was observed between the efficacy of influencer advertising and consumers' purchase intentions. Notably, female

respondents demonstrated a more substantial perception of social media influencers than male counterparts, attributed to higher internet usage among women.

The study conducted by Bare et al., (2021) from Mapúa University provides an insightful comparison of three major Online Food Delivery (OFD) applications in the Philippines: GrabFood, FoodPanda, and Pick.A.Roo, employing the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP). Key findings indicate FoodPanda as the superior choice based on various criteria, with Pick.A.Roo and GrabFood following respectively. Despite its overall top ranking, FoodPanda was noted to lag in areas such as security, order accuracy, and customer service. In contrast, Pick.A.Roo stood out for its premium features ensuring robust information security, while GrabFood excelled in customer service. The study underscores delivery time as the most influential criterion for OFD preference, which is significantly impacted by Manila's notorious traffic congestion. Additionally, the emphasis on the security and privacy of user data and the diverse availability of food and restaurant choices were highlighted as crucial for users.

According to the article written by Shaw (2022), the objective of Grab Philippines advertisements was to use the YouTube channel to attract and retain customers, communicate their value proposition, and encourage users to choose Grab over alternatives. The film, which features an albularyo, shows how comfortable Grab drivers are with their clients because they frequently bring food using GrabUnlimited's Daily Free Delivery service. The movie emphasizes how talkative and kind Filipinos are, emphasizing the bond Grab drivers develop with their customers. Since the movie's debut, it has had over 7,700,000 views and 234,000 comments. Additionally, it emphasizes the advantages of GrabUnlimited, a monthly membership plan that includes free GrabFood delivery for just PHP 9.

Grab Philippines engages viewers with compelling YouTube advertisements that combine convenient features, emotive narrative, and promotions. "Our Grab advertisements report shows a surge in user activity one week before the day itself, across the region, as people start looking for ways to make this day extra special for their loved ones," (Jennie Johnson, May 2023). Mother's Day often coincides with religious celebrations, making it an important time to gather family and express love and gratitude. Many people use these platforms to share their Mother's Day celebrations, spreading love and gratitude towards their mothers. They emphasize relevant situations, streamline daily tasks, and provide special offers in an effort to gain viewers' trust and boost user engagement and ultimately persuade them to utilize Grab for delivery and transportation.

Research Questions

Research Question no. 1: What was the profile of the respondents in terms of:

- 1.1. Sex
- 1.2. Age
- 1.3. Location

Research Question no. 2: FoodPanda Purchasing Intention

2.1 Did the content and quality of the message in the Foodpanda advertisement influence purchasing decisions?

2.2 Did external factors like catchy music or attractive endorsers from Foodpanda influence purchasing decisions?

2.3 Did watching YouTube advertisements from Foodpanda influence purchasing decisions?

2.4 Did frequent viewing of YouTube advertisements from Foodpanda influence the purchasing decisions?

2.5 Did the overall YouTube advertisement from Foodpanda influence the purchasing decisions of the respondents?

Research Question no. 3: Grab Purchasing Intention

3.1 Did the content and quality of the message in the advertisement from Grab influence purchasing decisions?

3.2 Did external factors like catchy music or attractive endorsers from Grab influence purchasing decisions?

3.3 Did watching YouTube advertisements from Grab influence purchasing decisions?

3.4 Did frequent viewing of YouTube advertisements from Grab influence the purchasing decisions of the respondents?

3.5 Did the overall Youtube advertisement from Grab influence the purchasing decisions?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher used a quantitative research approach, which is the process of collecting and analyzing numerical data (Bhandari, 2023). Quantitative research provides researchers with the tools to test hypotheses and make generalizations about a population based on the collected data. By employing statistical analysis, researchers can identify patterns, relationships, and trends within the data, allowing them to draw conclusions and make predictions. Moreover, quantitative research often employs large sample sizes to enhance the reliability and validity of the findings. The researchers utilize a quasi-experimental design due to the limitations in randomly assigning consumers to exposure to specific advertisements. The quasi-experimental design offers a valuable approach to examine the effectiveness of Food Panda and Grab YouTube advertisements in influencing consumer purchasing intentions (Thomas, 2020).

Research Locale

The research was conducted at the convenience of the researchers' homes, utilizing internet platforms. Transitioned from traditional paper surveys to a new set of

questions that respondents answered using their preferred digital devices. The survey for this particular study took place within Metro Manila. A total of one hundred (100) consumers were selected as the target group. The main objective of this study was to examine the effectiveness of YouTube advertisements for Food Panda and Grab Food on the purchasing intention of the consumers. The study aims to provide a full understanding of the effectiveness of YouTube advertisements related to these people. Furthermore, the study sheds light on the shifting environment of consumer behavior in the digital age. To reach the participants, the researchers distributed questionnaire links through various social media platforms, with a primary emphasis on using Facebook Messenger.

Population and Sampling

Purposive sampling, a non-probability sampling method, is employed in this study. It involves selecting units based on characteristics deemed necessary for the research (Jordan, 2021). Specifically, purposive sampling is applied to ensure that the sample closely aligns with the aims and objectives of the study, thus enhancing the credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability of the data and results. This method is chosen because it enables the selection of samples that are more representative of the population of interest, which in this case includes consumers exposed to YouTube advertisements by Food Panda and Grab.

The study involves 100 respondents, with 50 individuals having watched Grab's YouTube advertisements and another 50 exposed to Food Panda's advertisements. The age range of these respondents is between 18 and 54 years. This age range is supported by the article of Google/Ipsos (2018) which observed in the US for about 2953 consumers within this age bracket, including 87 YouTube viewers and 86 TV viewers. Furthermore, an article by ComScore (2017) found that audiences exposed to 5 or more YouTube advertising exposures between 2-6 days prior to an event had a 133% higher likelihood of viewership. Thus, this emphasize the significance of frequent exposure to YouTube ads in the days leading up to the premiere, lending credence to the chosen respondent profile for this study.

Research Ethics

According to Mager & Galandini (2020), research ethics are a set of principles and rules that define and regulate the design, conduct, management, use, and dissemination of any research involving living things like people as well as animals. The term 'research' is used widely in these guidelines. It consists of descriptive and exploratory investigations of social issues of interest. Also, it consists of activities conducted as part of observing, analyzing, and taking responsibility. Research must be carried out with integrity and openness. Lastly, any type of harassment, discrimination, threats, exploitation, or abuse must be addressed in research ethics, and situations of power and unequal interactions between people shouldn't be misused in any way. The researchers consider the ethical implications of any kind of research and prioritize the safety of the respondent. The main goal of the researchers is to respect the privacy of the respondents and ensure that their privacy would not be shared with anyone incorrectly. Also, researchers consider the

participation of the respondents. Researchers ensured that the participation in the studies was voluntary, informed, and, most importantly, that the respondent was safe for the research subject. Researchers conduct the research in a way that respects the rights and dignity of the participants.

Research Instruments

Online Questionnaire

The primary research tool utilized for this investigation is an online questionnaire, specifically designed and disseminated through Google Forms. This digital platform offers several advantages including easy accessibility for the respondents, the ability to reach a broad audience without geographic limitations, and automated data collection and storage, thereby increasing the efficiency and reliability of the study (Bryman, 2016). The questionnaire was comprehensive, addressing multiple facets pertinent to the research objectives. It included sections aimed at gathering demographic data, questions focused on examining the effectiveness of YouTube advertisements, as well as queries designed to understand the impact of external elements like music and visuals in shaping consumer behavior.

Likert Scale (McLeod, 2023)

To further refine the data collection process and elicit nuanced responses, the Likert Scale is employed as a key part of the questionnaire. Originated by Rensis Likert in 1932, this psychometric scale is particularly effective in survey research for gauging public opinion by providing multiple response options, usually ranging from "Strongly Agree", "Agree", "Disagree", and "Strongly Disagree" (McLeod, 2023). The use of the Likert Scale allows for a more detailed and quantifiable understanding of individual attitudes and preferences regarding the impact of advertisements on purchasing decisions. By integrating these responses with the categorical data obtained through demographic questions, the research aims to construct a multi-dimensional perspective that supports advanced statistical analysis. This enables the drawing of robust and comprehensive conclusions, thereby adding greater depth and validity to the study.

Data Collection

For this research, data was collected through the administration of surveys. Survey-based data collection involves gathering information from specific respondents with the aim of making generalizations to a wider population. As stated by Simplilearn (2023), data collection is the process of systematically gathering and analyzing information from various sources to address research questions, identify trends, and assess probabilities. Surveys offer a versatile means of gathering information, and researchers can collect data from respondents both locally and globally, enriching the study with valuable insights to achieve its objectives. Furthermore, surveys allow for the effective analysis of multiple variables. The researchers gathered data from a wide range of participants and conducted the survey through Google form including the informed consent, screening tool, as well as the survey questionnaire, individually distributing it to

the chosen respondents after passing the screening tool. After the data collected, the researchers proceeded with the data analysis using mean, standard deviation, and SPSS and created a conclusion and recommendation based on the result. This study yielded valuable information that was crucial to achieving its objectives.

Data Analysis

Mean

The mean is a dataset of the sum of all values divided by the total number of values. It is the most commonly used measure of central tendency and is often referred to as the “average.” It is a way to summarize a data set by providing a single, representative value that gives an idea of the “typical” value within the data. The researcher often collects data from samples and performs inferential statistics to understand the population they came from. (Bhandari, 2020).

Standard Deviation

Standard deviation is a statistic that measures the dispersion of a dataset relative to its mean and is calculated as the square root of the variance. The standard deviation is calculated as the square root of variance by determining each data point's deviation relative to the mean. If the data points are further from the mean, there is a higher deviation within the data set; thus, the more spread out the data, the higher the standard deviation. Standard deviation is calculated by taking the square root of a value derived from comparing data points to a collective mean of a population. (Hargrave, 2023).

Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS)

SPSS is a software package that is accessible to researchers without extensive programming or statistical background. It is widely used in academia, market research, and various other fields within the social sciences. Researchers and data analysts use SPSS to perform various data-related tasks, such as data entry, data cleaning, data manipulation, and statistical analysis. It is a powerful tool for social science research due to its user-friendly interface, extensive statistical capabilities, and data visualization tools.

Multiple Regression Analysis

The researchers employed regression analysis to examine how the study variables affected respondents' purchasing decisions, which is a statistical technique that can be used to analyze the relationship between a single dependent variable and several independent variables. The objective of multiple regression analysis is to use the independent variables whose values are known to predict the value of the single dependent value (Blokhin, 2023).

RESULTS

This section shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents according to their Sex, Age, and Location. A total of 100 respondents within Metro Manila who have watched FoodPanda/Grab Advertisements were included in the study.

Demographic Profile

4.1 Table 1: Respondent's Sex

	Sex	Frequency	
	Percentage		
<i>Grab</i>	Female	34	68%
	Male	16	32%
Total:		50	100%
<i>Food Panda</i>	Female	26	52%
	Male	24	48%
Total:		50	100%

Table 1 presents the respondents' sex. The majority for the Grab and FoodPanda respondents were female, having a total of 34 or 68% of the total respondents and 26 or 52%, respectively. The remaining 16 from Grab and 24 from FoodPanda were males. This implies that among the respondents within Metro Manila who have watched FoodPanda/Grab Advertisements were females.

4.1 Table 2: Respondent's Age

	Age	Frequency	
	Percentage		
<i>Grab</i>	18-24	40	80%
	25-34	9	18%
	45-54	1	2%
Total:		50	100%
<i>Food Panda</i>	18-24	38	76%
	25-34	11	22%
	35-44	1	2%
Total:		50	100%

The frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents' age is shown in Table 1.2. The majority of the respondents were aged 18-24 years old. Among the respondents from Grab, 40 (80%) of them fell in this age group and 38 (76%) respondents from FoodPanda. There were also 9 respondents in the Grab application who stated that their age is between 25-34 years old. The remaining one respondent fell in the age group 45-54 years old. Meanwhile, of the respondents from the FoodPanda, 11 of them stated that their age is between 25-34 years old and the remaining one respondents aged 35-44 years old. This implies that among respondents within Metro Manila who have watched FoodPanda/Grab Advertisements were young adults.

4.1 Table 3: Respondent's Location

	Age Percentage	Frequency	
<i>Grab</i>	YES	50	100%
<i>Food Panda</i>	YES	50	100%
Total:		100	100%

Table 1.3 presents the current location of the 100 respondents. All of them stated that they lived within Metro Manila and watched FoodPanda/Grab Advertisements for the past two weeks.

4.2 Table 4: Descriptives of FoodPanda Application

This section discusses the respondents' level of agreement towards the factors that affect their purchasing decision for FoodPanda application in terms of its Content and Quality, External Factors, Influence Level, and Frequency of Viewings, and Purchasing Decision.

Variables	Frequency	Mean	SD
Content and Quality	4	3.11	0.67
External Factors	4	3.18	0.63
Influence Level	4	3.10	0.68
Frequency of Viewing	4	3.11	0.74
Purchasing Decision	4	3.01	0.77

4.2 Table 5: Descriptives of Grab Application

This section discusses the respondents' level of agreement towards the factors that affect their purchasing decision for Grab application in terms of its Content and Quality, External Factors, Influence Level, and Frequency of Viewings, and Purchasing Decision.

Variables	Frequency	Mean	SD
Content and Quality	4	3.30	0.67
External Factors	4	3.20	0.67
Influence Level	4	3.32	0.68
Frequency of Viewing	4	3.25	0.68
Purchasing Decision	4	3.28	0.65

Table 6.1
FoodPanda Application (Content and Quality of the Message)

Variable	Pearson Correlation	P-Value	Unstandardized beta	Decision Rule and Interpretation
Content and Quality and Purchasing Decision predictor	0.786	<0.01	0.214	Reject Ho1.1: The content and quality of the message are a significant predictor of purchasing decisions.

The table above illustrates how content and quality of the message affects purchase decisions. The researchers obtained a p-value of <0.01, which transmits the interpretation of the data given via linear regression. The null hypothesis was rejected after taking into consideration the decision criterion that advises researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the significant difference is bigger than 0.05. As a result, content and quality of the message are a significant predictor of purchasing decisions. There is also a positive weak correlation (0.786) between the two variables, and each unit of content and quality of the message increases purchase decision by 0.214.

*Table 6.2
FoodPanda Application (External Factors)*

Variable Rule Interpretation	Pearson Correlation	P-Value	Unstandardized beta	Decision and
External Factors and Purchasing predictor Decision decisions.	0.845	<0.01	0.159	Reject Ho1.2: The external factors is a significant of purchasing

The table above illustrates how external factors affect purchase decisions. The researchers obtained a p-value of <0.01, which transmits the interpretation of the data given via linear regression. The null hypothesis was rejected after taking into consideration the decision criterion that advises researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the significant difference is bigger than 0.05. As a result, external factors are a significant predictor of purchasing decisions. There is also a positive weak correlation (0.845) between the two variables, and each unit of external factors increases purchase decision by 0.159.

*Table 6.3
FoodPanda Application (Influence Level)*

Variable Rule Interpretation	Pearson Correlation	P-Value	Unstandardized beta	Decision and
Influence Level and Purchasing predictor Decision decisions.	0.881	<0.01	0.476	Reject Ho1.3: The influence level is a significant of purchasing

The table above illustrates how influence level affect purchase decisions. The researchers obtained a p-value of <0.01, which transmits the interpretation of the data given via linear regression. The null hypothesis was rejected after taking into consideration the decision criterion that advises researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the significant difference is bigger than 0.05. As a result, influence level is a significant

predictor of purchasing decisions. There is also a positive weak correlation (0.881) between the two variables, and each unit of influence level increases purchase decision by 0.476.

*Table 6.4
FoodPanda Application (Frequency of Viewings)*

Variable Rule	Pearson Correlation	P-Value	Unstandardized beta	Decision and Interpretation
Frequency of Viewings and Purchasing Decision	0.849	<0.01	0.234	Reject Ho1.4: The frequency of viewings is a significant predictor of purchasing decisions.

The table above illustrates how frequency of viewings affect purchase decisions. The researchers obtained a p-value of <0.01, which transmits the interpretation of the data given via linear regression. The null hypothesis was rejected after taking into consideration the decision criterion that advises researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the significant difference is bigger than 0.05. As a result, frequency of viewings is a significant predictor of purchasing decisions. There is also a positive weak correlation (0.849) between the two variables, and each unit of frequency of viewings increases purchase decision by 0.234.

*Table 6.5
Grab Application (Content and Quality of the Message)*

Variable Rule	Pearson Correlation	P-Value	Unstandardized beta	Decision and Interpretation
Content and Quality and Purchasing Decision	0.771	<0.01	0.105	Reject Ho2.1: The content and quality of the message are a significant predictor

of purchasing decisions.

The table above illustrates how content and quality of the message affects purchase decisions. The researchers obtained a p-value of <0.01, which transmits the interpretation of the data given via linear regression. The null hypothesis was rejected after taking into consideration the decision criterion that advises researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the significant difference is bigger than 0.05. As a result, content and quality of the message are a significant predictor of purchasing decisions. There is also a positive weak correlation (0.771) between the two variables, and each unit of content and quality of the message increases purchase decision by 0.105.

*Table 6.6
Grab Application (External Factors)*

Variable Rule	Pearson Correlation	P-Value	Unstandardized beta	Decision and Interpretation
External Factors	0.749	<0.01	0.011	Reject Ho2.2: The external factors is a significant predictor of purchasing Decision decisions.

The table above illustrates how external factors affect purchase decisions. The researchers obtained a p-value of <0.01, which transmits the interpretation of the data given via linear regression. The null hypothesis was rejected after taking into consideration the decision criterion that advises researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the significant difference is bigger than 0.05. As a result, external factors are a significant predictor of purchasing decisions. There is also a positive weak correlation (0.749) between the two variables, and each unit of external factors increases purchase decision by 0.011.

*Table 6.7
Grab Application (Influence Level)*

Variable Rule	Pearson	P-Value	Unstandardized	Decision
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Variable	Correlation	P-Value	beta	Decision and Interpretation
Influence Level and Purchasing predictor Decision decisions.	0.846	<0.01	0.146	Reject Ho2.3: The influence level is a significant of purchasing

The table above illustrates how influence level affect purchase decisions. The researchers obtained a p-value of <0.01, which transmits the interpretation of the data given via linear regression. The null hypothesis was rejected after taking into consideration the decision criterion that advises researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the significant difference is bigger than 0.05. As a result, influence level is a significant predictor of purchasing decisions. There is also a positive weak correlation (0.846) between the two variables, and each unit of influence level increases purchase decision by 0.146.

Table 6.8
Grab Application (Frequency of Viewings)

Variable	Pearson	P-Value	Unstandardized	Decision
Rule	Correlation		beta	and
Interpretation				
Frequency of Viewings and Purchasing predictor Decision decisions.	0.887	<0.01	0.624	Reject Ho2.4: The frequency of is a significant of purchasing

The table above illustrates how frequency of viewings affect purchase decisions. The researchers obtained a p-value of <0.01, which transmits the interpretation of the data given via linear regression. The null hypothesis was rejected after taking into consideration the decision criterion that advises researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the significant difference is bigger than 0.05. As a result, frequency of viewings is a significant predictor of purchasing decisions. There is also a positive weak correlation (0.887) between the two variables, and each unit of frequency of viewings increases purchase decision by 0.624.

DISCUSSION

Conclusions

This research study examined the effectiveness of YouTube advertisements of Food Panda and Grab on consumer purchasing intentions of the respondents within Metro Manila who have watched their advertisements for the last two weeks using the four factors namely: Content and Quality, External Factors, Influence Level, and Frequency of Viewings. Results found that YouTube advertisements had an impact on the purchasing decisions of the respondents and the four variables that were utilized in the research were significant contributors to this influence.

Furthermore, the findings reveal that the purchasing decision of the respondents towards FoodPanda/Grab is increased by each unit of the independent variables that were included in the advertisement that was released on YouTube. Positive Pearson coefficients indicate that when the value of one variable increases, the value of the other variable also tends to increase. In terms of FoodPanda YouTube Advertisements, the lowest key element is the Content and quality which have a Pearson Correlation of 0.786 that implies that the more positive content and quality advertisements present on FoodPanda YouTube advertisements, the more respondents will choose FoodPanda as their service. Additionally, the highest key contributor for the FoodPanda is the Influence Level which has a Pearson Correlation of 0.881 which implies that the Influence Level of the YouTube Ads give a significant impact on the purchasing decisions of the respondents. Moreover, in terms of Grab Ads, the lowest variable computed was its External Factors which has a Pearson Coefficient of 0.749 also indicates a strong relationship with the purchasing decisions of the respondents. On the other hand, the highest key contributor for the Grab YouTube Ads was the Frequency of Viewing 0.887 that holds a very strong relationship between the purchasing decision of the respondents, this implies that the more respondents saw the Grab YouTube advertisements, the more likely they will use this service. Thus, this concludes that all four variables have an impact and a significant predictor on the purchasing decisions of the respondents on the FoodPanda/Grab based on their YouTube Advertisements.

Recommendations

Recommendation Based on the Findings

The purpose of this study is to examine the effectiveness of YouTube Advertisements of Food Panda and Grab with the use of 4 variables. The findings stated above shows that YouTube advertisements had an impact on the purchasing decisions of the respondents. The researchers suggest that businesses or companies should use YouTube Ads as a platform for promotional campaigns and for them to be able to attract more customers. As a given example from the Food Panda Application, the lowest variable was content and quality which indicates that a company must focus on creating

informative or persuasive messages to gain the attention of their target audience and optimize YouTube advertisement length and placement, and add interactive elements to drive curiosity and conversions. Based on the Grab Application, the highest variable was frequency of viewings, which leads to the suggestion that businesses or companies should make their YouTube advertisements appear consistently to make the target market remember them. In addition to this, regularly engaged viewers present opportunities for deeper brand storytelling, exclusive product reveals, or personalized retargeting campaigns. This fosters loyalty, boosts conversion rates, and keeps them coming back for more, turning casual viewers into ardent brand advocates.

Recommendation for Future Research

To advance the researchers understanding of the impact of digital marketing strategies within the context of the competitive food delivery industry, it is recommended that future research explores the effectiveness of YouTube advertisements specifically created by Food Panda and Grab on consumer purchasing intentions. This research adopted a quantitative method to provide a comprehensive analysis. Surveys and data analytics could be employed to quantify the influence of YouTube advertisements on consumer decision-making, measuring metrics such as click-through rates, conversion rates, and brand recall. Additionally, investigating the role of demographic factors, cultural preferences, and geographic location in shaping consumer attitudes towards these advertisements would enrich the study's findings. This research has the potential to not only contribute valuable insights to the academic literature on digital marketing and consumer behavior but also offer practical recommendations for marketers in the food delivery industry seeking to optimize their advertising strategies and enhance consumer engagement on the YouTube platform.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research was conducted with the utmost ethical regard for the participants. Informed consent was obtained prior to any data collection, and participants were guaranteed the freedom to withdraw from the study at any point without facing repercussions. Their anonymity was carefully protected throughout the research process, and their well-being was prioritized at all times. Potential conflicts of interest were identified and proactively managed to ensure the integrity of the findings. Stringent measures were taken to avoid plagiarism, and the interpretation of the data was conducted objectively and free from bias. Finally, it is unequivocally stated that the results of this research were used solely for academic purposes and not for any personal gain or agenda. In summary, the researchers were committed to upholding the highest ethical standards throughout the entire study.

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